

ISSN 2181-2357

XALQARO NAZARIY VA AMALIY TADQIQOTLAR
JURNALI

INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF THEORETICAL AND PRACTICAL RESEARCH

JURNAL FARG'ONA POLITEXNIKA
INSTITUTI HAMKORLIGIDA NASHR
ETILADI

VOLUME 2,
Issue 11
2022

«Al-Ferganus» MChJ.

A. M. Abdullayev

«Nazariy va amaliy tadqiqotlar xalqaro jurnali»

Ilmiy jurnal.

2021 yil noyabrdan beri nashr etilmoqda.

Oyiga bir marta nashr etiladi. 16+

2-tom, 11 -son.

Noyabr 2022 y.

Tahririyat kengashi raisi Salomov O'ktam Raximovich, Rector of FerPI

Bosh muharrir K. I. Kurpayanidi

Tahririyat hay'ati: A.M.Abdullaev, M.S.Ashurov, E.A.Mo'minova, K.X.Abduraxmonov, A.N.Asaul, A.V.Burkov, U.V.G'ofurov, M.A.Ikromov, D.Kudbiev, E.S.Margianiti, B.Obrenovich, L.NA Sultonov, L.NA. , A.Xasanov, Sh.T.Karimov, Sh.Sh.Salixanova, U.K.Alimov, S.M.Turabdjano, B.A.Alimatov, R.J.Tozhiyev, A.A.Risqulov, B.M.Tursunov, S. F. Ergashev, J.D.Axmedov, Kh.A. Akramov, M.X. Xakimov, Sh.M. Iskandarova, Z.M. Sobirova, A.M. Muxtarova, L.M. Babakhodjaeva..

Tahririyat manzili: 150107

Farg'ona shahri, Farg'ona ko'chasi, 86 -
uy

Тел. +998971003888

<https://alferganus.uz/en/site/index>

E-mail: alferganus.ltd@gmail.com

IF(Impact Factor) **8.7 / 2021**
<http://journalseeker.researchbib.com/view/issn/2181-2357>

TOGETHER WE REACH THE GOAL
SJIF 2022: 5,962
<http://sjifactor.com/passport.php?id=21994>

O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidenti administratsiyasi huzuridagi axborot va ommaviy kommunikatsiyalar agentligida ro'yxatga olingan.

Ro'yxatga olish № 1189 Berilgan sanasi: 17-06-2021.

Xalqaro nazariy va amaliy tadqiqotlar jurnali Crossref, OpenAIRE, Google Scholar bazalariga kiritilgan.

Impact-faktor 2021 Evaluation Pending

CC litsenziyasi turi: Attribution 4.0 International (CC BY 4.0).

Jurnal jahon va mintaqaviy darajada fan va amaliyotning rivojlanish masalalariga bag'ishlangan.

Jurnal olimlar, o'qituvchilar, doktorantlar, talabalar uchun mo'ljallangan.

Nazariy va amaliy tadqiqotlar xalqaro jurnali.

2022. T. 2. №11. <https://alferganus.uz>

ISSN 2181-2357

9 772181 235007 >

© «Al-Ferganus» MChJ,
2022 Farg'ona, O'zbekiston

License type supported CC: Attribution 4.0 International (CC BY 4.0)

«Al-Ferganus» LLC.
A. M. Abdullaev
“International journal of theoretical and practical research”
Scientific Journal.
Published since November 2021.
Schedule: monthly. 16+

Volume 2, Issue 11

November, 2022.

Chairman of the Editorial Board Salomov Uktam Rakhimovich, FarPI rektori

Editor-in-chief K. I. Kurpayanidi

Editorial Board: A. M. Abdullaev, M. S. Ashurov, E. A. Muminova, K. Kh. Abdurakhmanov, A. N. Asaul, A. V. Burkov, U. V. Gafurov, M. A. Ikramov, D. Kudbiev, E. S. Margianiti, B. Obrenovich, L. Ivars, K. E. Onarkulov, N. A. Sultanov, A. Khasanov, Sh. T. Karimov, Sh. Sh. Khamdamova, D. S. Salikhanova, U.K. Alimov, S.M. Turabdzhanov, B.A.Alimatov, R.Zh. Tozhiev, A.A. Riskulov, B.M. Tursunov, A.A. Shermukhamedov, S. F. Ergashev, J.D.Akhmedov, Kh.A. Akramov, M.Kh. Khakimov, Sh.M. Iskandarova, Z.M. Sobirova, A.M. Mukhtarova, L.M. Babakhodzhaeva.

Address of the editorial office:

150107

Fergana city, Fergana str., 86.

Phone +998971003888

<https://alferganus.uz/en/site/index>

E-mail:

alferganus.ltd@gmail.com

IF(Impact Factor) **8.7 / 2021**

<http://journalseeker.researchbib.com/view/issn/2181-2357>

TOGETHER WE REACH THE GOAL
SJIF 2022: 5,962

<http://sjifactor.com/passport.php?id=21994>

Registered with the Agency of Information and Mass Communications under the Administration of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan.
Registration No. 1189 dated 17-06-2021.

The journal "International Journal of Theoretical and Practical Research" is included Crossref, OpenAIRE, Google Scholar.

Impact-factor 2021 Evaluation Pending

License type supported CC: Attribution 4.0 International (CC BY 4.0).

The Journal addresses issues of global and regional Science and Practice. For scientists, teachers, doctoral students, students.

(2022). International journal of theoretical and practical research, 2(11).

<https://alferganus.uz>

ISSN 2181-2357

9 772181 235007 >

© LLC «Al-Ferganus»,
2022, Fergana, Uzbekistan

License type supported CC: Attribution 4.0 International (CC BY 4.0)

«Al-Ferganus» ООО.

А. М. Абдуллаев

«Международный журнал теоретических и практических исследований»

Научный журнал.

Издается с ноября 2021 г.

Выходит один раз в месяц. 16+

Том 2, Номер 11.

Ноябрь 2022 г.

Председатель редакционного совета Саломов Уктам Рахимович, ректор ФерПИ

Главный редактор К. И. Курпаяниди

Редакционная коллегия: А.М.Абдуллаев, М.С.Ашуров, Э.А.Муминова, К.Х.Абдурахманов, А.Н.Асаул, А.В.Бурков, У.В.Гафуров, М.А.Икрамов, Д.Кудбиев, Э.С.Маргианити, Б.Обренович, Л.Иварс, К.Э.Онаркулов, Н.А.Султанов, А.Хасанов, Ш.Т.Каримов, Ш.Ш.Хамдамова, Д.С.Салиханова, У.К.Алимов, С.М.Турабджанов, Б.А.Алиматов, Р.Ж.Тожиев, А.А.Рискулов, Б.М.Турсунов, А.А.Шермухамедов, С.Ф.Эргашев, Ж.Д.Ахмедов, Х.А.Акрамов, М.Х.Хахимов, Ш.М.Искандарова, З.М.Собирова, А.М.Мухтарова, Л.М.Бабаходжаева.

Адрес редакции: 150107

г. Фергана, ул. Ферганская, 86

Тел. +998971003888

<https://alferganus.uz/en/site/index>

E-mail: alferganus.ltd@gmail.com

IF(Impact Factor) **8.7 / 2021**

[http://journalseeker.research](http://journalseeker.researchbib.com/view/issn/2181-2357)

[bib.com/view/issn/2181-](http://journalseeker.researchbib.com/view/issn/2181-2357)

[2357](http://journalseeker.researchbib.com/view/issn/2181-2357)

TOGETHER WE REACH THE GOAL

SJIF 2022:5,962

[http://sjifactor.com/passp](http://sjifactor.com/passport.php?id=21994)

[ort.php?id=21994](http://sjifactor.com/passport.php?id=21994)

Зарегистрирован в Агентстве информации и массовых коммуникаций при Администрации

Президента Республики Узбекистан.

Регистрации № 1189 от 17-06-2021.

Журнал «Международный журнал теоретических и практических исследований» включен в Crossref, OpenAIRE, Google Scholar.

Импакт-факторы журнала: 2021 Evaluation Pending

Тип лицензии CC поддерживаемый журналом: Attribution 4.0 International (CC BY 4.0).

В журнале рассматриваются вопросы развития мировой и региональной науки и практики. Для ученых, преподавателей, докторантов, студентов.

Международный журнал теоретических и практических исследований. 2022. Т. 2. №11.

<https://alferganus.uz>

ISSN 2181-2357

9 772181 235007 >

©ООО «Al-Ferganus»,
2022, Фергана, Узбекистан

License type supported CC: Attribution 4.0 International (CC BY 4.0)

TABLE OF CONTENTS

Texnik fanlar / Technical sciences / Технические науки

1. **Amirov Tursoat Jumaevich** 7
Designations of the design age of road cement concrete
2. **Jurayev Uktam Shavkatovich, Akhmedov Jamoldin Djalolovich** 12
Estimation of the seismonegress state of underground structures by wave dynamics methods. Part 2
3. **Nishonov N. A., Rahimjonov Z. Q., Zokirov F. Z.** 18
Status of assessment of dynamic characteristics of intermediate devices of vehicle bridges
4. **Shoimqulov Asror Abdunabiyevich** 26
Advantages of test and functional diagnostics in troubleshooting traction asynchronous motors of electric locomotives
5. **Khakimov Shaukat, Samatov Rustam, Rajapova S.S.** 32
Legal basis and interactive services of the national geographic information system of Uzbekistan
6. **Yusupaliyev Umid, Amirov, Tursoat** 39
Construction methods of road base by gravel – sand mixture treated with cement the addition of bitumen emulsion
7. **Ziyaev Kamoliddin, Omarov Janserik** 47
Research of passenger traffic in public transport of the city of Urgench

Kimyoviy fanlar / Chemical Sciences / Химические науки

8. **Mamatkulov Mamatqul, Usmanov Botir, Jorayev Saidmahammadjon** 57
Vitamins and other physiologically active substances found in fish oil
9. **Usmanov Botir, Amanbayeva Gulzoda** 63
Study of the solubility of tricalcium phosphate in aqueous solutions of ammonium nitrate

Iqtisodiy fanlar / Economic Sciences/ Экономические науки

10. **Abdullaeva Barchinoy Yuldashevna** 72
Analysis of the experience of the EU countries in increasing the capital of credit institutions
11. **Abdullaeva Sevarakhon Khasanovna** 85
A system of indicators reflecting economic stability and their distinctive features
12. **Achilov Abror Niyatkobilovich** 94
Effectiveness of innovations in the management of information and communication technologies in the Republic of Uzbekistan
13. **Akhunova Marifat Khakimovna** 106
Marketing innovations in the economy: problems and development prospects
14. **Ashurov Makhhammadzhon, Ismailova Gulshoda** 113

- Conflict situations in the activities of the enterprise, ways of their reduction and management*
15. **Gaziev Xaydarali Ortikovich** 123
Improving the organization of environmental from the management of LLC "Avtooyana"
16. **Gafurova Faina Semyonovna** 131
Digital marketing in the business system
17. **Nabieva Nilufar Muratovna** 142
On the issues of bank support for export producers in Uzbekistan
18. **Kodirov Sardorbek** 153
The status of the digital process in Uzbekistan and the significance of international ratings in it
19. **Nosirov Ilkhom Abbosovich, Tashpulatova Munirakhon Mahmudovna, Rasulov Jasurbek** 161
Motivational mechanisms in higher education institutions, their role and significance
20. **Rasulov Nozimjon Nabijonovich** 169
Analysis of the use of marketing research in the footwear market
21. **Tuychieva Odina Nabieva** 180
The use of digital technologies to improve the efficiency of production processes
22. **Tukhtasinova Mukhayo Mirzasultonovna** 189
State stimulation of the development of innovative processes in the economy
23. **Shakirova Yulduz Saidaliyevna, Ashurov Makhammadzhon Sotvoldievich** 197
Features of use of business processes that simplify the organization of the work of the enterprise
24. **Shakirova Yulduz Saydalievna** 208
Modern banking system: defi models in the capital market
25. **Yormatov Ilmidin Toshmatovich** 215
The role of small enterprises and private entrepreneurs in the development of the economy of Uzbekistan

E'lon / Reklama / Advertisement

- Advertisement* 221
- Our publications* 228

QR CODE of this issue of the magazine

International journal of
theoretical and practical
research

Scientific Journal

Year: 2022 Issue: 11 Volume: 2

Published: 30.11.2022

<http://alferganus.uz>

Citation:

Achilov, A.N. (2022). Effectiveness of innovations in the management of information and communication technologies in the Republic of Uzbekistan. *SJ International journal of theoretical and practical research*, 2 (11), 94-105.

Achilov, A.N. (2022). Effectiveness of innovations in the management of information and communication technologies in the Republic of Uzbekistan. *Nazariy va amaliy tadqiqotlar xalqaro jurnali*, 2 (11), 94-105.

Doi:

<https://dx.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7391040>

Achilov, Abror Niyatkobilovich

PhD,

Docent, Department of Management,

Fergana Polytechnic Institute

E-mail: niyatqobil@mail.ru

UDC 338.45

EFFECTIVENESS OF INNOVATIONS IN THE MANAGEMENT OF INFORMATION AND COMMUNICATION TECHNOLOGIES IN THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN

Abstract. *This article describes a number of research on the development of information and communication technology enterprises, the management of innovative processes in the field of ICT in the context of globalization and the factors influencing this area. Formation of an integrated indicator of effective management of innovative processes in the field of ICT. Methods for evaluating the effectiveness of management of innovative processes in the field of information and communication technologies. The number of Internet users in Uzbekistan has exceeded 23 million, despite the slowdown in recent years. It also highlights the advantages of the regression model, in which the net profit of Uzbehtelecom JSC depends on the amount of investment in innovation.*

Keywords: *information and communication, innovation, internet, investment, e-government, computer literacy, human intellectual and creative activity, discoveries, inventions and innovators, global network, telecommunications, computer technology.*

Ачиллов, Аброр Ниятқобиллович

PhD, доцент,

Кафедра “Менеджмент”

Ферганский политехнический институт

E-mail: niyatqobil@mail.ru

ЭФФЕКТИВНОСТЬ ИННОВАЦИЙ В УПРАВЛЕНИИ ИНФОРМАЦИОННО-КОММУНИКАЦИОННЫМИ ТЕХНОЛОГИЯМИ В РЕСПУБЛИКЕ УЗБЕКИСТАН

Аннотация. В данной статье описан ряд исследований, посвященных развитию предприятий информационно-коммуникационных технологий, управлению инновационными процессами в сфере ИКТ в условиях глобализации и факторам, влияющим на эту сферу. Формирование интегрального показателя эффективности управления инновационными процессами в сфере ИКТ. Методы оценки эффективности управления инновационными процессами в сфере информационно-коммуникационных технологий. Количество интернет-пользователей в Узбекистане превысило 23 миллиона, несмотря на спад в последние годы. Также выделены преимущества регрессионной модели, в которой чистая прибыль АО «Узбектелеком» зависит от суммы инвестиций в инновации.
Ключевые слова: информация и связь, инновации, интернет, инвестиции, электронное правительство, компьютерная грамотность, интеллектуальная и творческая активность человека, открытия, изобретения и рационализаторы, глобальная сеть, телекоммуникации, компьютерные технологии.

Achilov, Abror Niyatqobilovich
PhD,
Menejment kafedراسи dotsenti,
Farg'ona Politexnika Instituti

О'ZBEKISTON RESPUBLIKASIDA AXBOROT-KOMMUNIKATSIYA TEKNOLOGIYALARINI BOSHQARISHDAGI INNOVATSIYALARNING SAMARADORLIGI

Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqolada axborot-kommunikatsiya texnologiyalari korxonalarini rivojlantirish, globallashtirish sharoitida AKT sohasidagi innovatsion jarayonlarni boshqarish va ushbu sohaga ta'sir etuvchi omillarga oid qator tadqiqotlar bayon etilgan. AKT sohasida innovatsion jarayonlarni samarali boshqarishning yaxlit ko'rsatkichini shakllantirish. Axborot-kommunikatsiya texnologiyalari sohasida innovatsion jarayonlarni boshqarish samaradorligini baholash usullari. O'zbekistonda internet foydalanuvchilari soni so'nggi yillarda sekinlashganiga qaramay, 23 milliondan oshdi. Shuningdek, "O'zbektelekom" AK sof foydasi innovatsiyalarga yo'naltirilgan investitsiyalar hajmiga bog'liq bo'lgan regressiya modelining afzalliklariga alohida e'tibor qaratiladi.

Kalit so'zlar: axborot va kommunikatsiya, innovatsiyalar, internet, sarmoya, elektron hukumat, kompyuter savodxonligi, insonning intellektual va ijodiy faoliyati, kashfiyotlar, ixtirolovchi va innovatorlar, global tarmoq, telekommunikatsiya, kompyuter texnologiyalari.

Introduction.

An important aspect of economic reforms in the world is the development of the digital economy based on information and communication technologies, which are one of the most important elements of a market economy in the era of globalization. In the world, almost 60% of the total cost of innovation is in the field of information and communication technologies.²

A number of research projects on the development of information and communication technology enterprises in the context of globalization, including the role of infrastructure in the provision of products and services, the impact of ICT on the world market and the digital economy, e-government, online services Extensive research is being conducted to study the management of innovative processes in the field of ICT. In this regard, special attention should be paid to the application of experience gained in international practice and the management of the infrastructure of enterprises in the field of ICT in the country. Improving the scientific basis for improving efficiency, developing a methodology for evaluating the effectiveness of management of innovative processes is one of the most pressing issues today.

Analysis of the literature on the subject:

Ilenkovoy S.D. According to him, innovation processes are considered as a process of preparation and implementation of innovative changes, consisting of interrelated stages as a result of the emergence of current innovations.

Zavlina P.N. An innovation process is a process of transforming scientific knowledge into innovations, in which innovations can be expressed as a chain of events that transitions from an idea to a specific product, technology or service and is disseminated in practical use.

Stig Ottosson The process from idea to commercial product is called innovation process.

Approaching the above considerations, we have interpreted the economic classification of the term innovation process as follows: Innovation process is the process of translating scientific knowledge into practical application of an innovative idea with human intellectual and creative activity, discoveries, inventions and rationalization proposals.³

Research methodology:

With the development of the Internet during the pandemic, the development of the ICT sector is accelerating. The widespread use of ICT in various sectors of the economy has become one of the key factors in improving the socio-economic status of society, stabilizing economic growth. The rapid growth of the global Internet has led to an increase in computer literacy among the general population, the widespread popularity of telecommunications, computer technology and other new means of communication, as well as effective means of exchanging information through the global network. The rapid growth of the process of implementation of innovative products and services has confirmed the expediency of considering the effective management of this sector.

² <https://www.itu.int>

³ Author's development.

Modernization of the ICT sector and the development of innovative processes will allow the construction of e-government, the development of the digital economy, increase the efficiency of government and increase the competitiveness of the country's economy.

Fig. 1 Factors influencing the management of innovation processes in the field of information and communication technologies⁴

These factors will help to identify areas that affect the development of innovative activities in the field of ICT, as well as management approaches.

Today, the structure of innovative processes in the field of ICT includes: the emergence of mobile communications and the Internet; mobile internet development; development of mobile applications; creation of cloud technologies; e-commerce and e-business development; 3G and 4G mobile internet development; Introduction of Wi-Fi technologies; mass introduction of intelligent platform services; IoT - (Internet of Things) Internet of Things; BigData popularity; proliferation of chat bots and corporate information systems; 5G will be introduced; development of the digital economy.

⁴Developed by the authors

In recent years, the world experience has a number of ways to assess the innovative development of countries, in which the development of the ICT sector plays an important role. However, there are no indicators of innovative development of the ICT sector. In order to assess the management of innovation processes in the field of ICT, the author selected a number of international indices that reflect the state of management of innovation processes in countries and the results of management in the field of ICT.

Figure 2. Formation of an integrated indicator of effective management of innovative processes in the field of ICT ⁵

In the management of innovation processes in the field of ICT, the indicators in the structure of international indices are assessed by determining the integral indicator and comparing it with the share of the ICT sector in GDP. It should be noted that the country does not have a perfect index that reflects the management of innovation processes in the country, especially in the field of ICT, one of the reasons is that constantly introduced new technologies are evaluated by new criteria and reflected in different countries.

Analysis and results:

⁵Developed by the authors

The obtained data form the management of innovation processes in the field of ICT based on the indicators of the global index of cybersecurity, the level of readiness for e-government, the level of global innovation development and ICT development. It should be noted that each of these indices to some extent covers the innovative development of ICT in the country, and as a result, these ratings reflect the effectiveness of the management of innovation processes in the ICT sector of the country. By studying these indices, the author developed indicators to assess the effectiveness of innovation process management in the field of ICT and proposed an assessment methodology.

Figure 3. Methods for assessing the effectiveness of management of innovative processes in the field of information and communication technologies in Uzbekistan ⁶

Indicators for assessing the effectiveness of innovative processes in the field of ICT in Uzbekistan include indicators of innovative communication, indicators of human capital involved in innovation processes, indicators of digital business, indicators of innovative goods and services.

⁶Developed by the authors

Indicators and methodology for assessing the effectiveness of innovative process management in the field of information and communication technologies were developed by the author and researched in the second chapter of the dissertation.

We can know the management of innovation processes in our country by evaluating the results of innovative activities. In the previous section, we looked at evaluating innovation through global indexes and rankings. Innovative activity in the country is assessed by a number of indicators. In the field of ICT, the dynamics of the development of ICT infrastructure can be cited as a result of the management of innovative processes. This is due to the fact that through the regulation and introduction of innovative activities, many results can be achieved, such as increasing the speed of the Internet, attracting the wider use of Internet and mobile services, the development of digital television, the provision of electronic services.

Table 1**Development of ICT infrastructure in our country⁷**

№	Indicators	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022
1	Mobile coverage	45	70	86	96%	98%
2	Broadband coverage of mobile communication	23	44	58	70%	72%
3	Number of mobile users	20.6	21.4	22.8	23.8 mln	24 mln
4	Number of Internet users	17	18	20	22 mln	23 mln
5	Number of mobile Internet users	11	14	17	19 mln	21 mln

As for the results of 2022, mobile coverage has reached 98%, while broadband coverage has reached 72%. The number of Internet users has also exceeded 23 million to date, despite a slowdown in growth in recent years.

As a result of the research, the current situation was analyzed in accordance with the methodology proposed by the author to assess the effectiveness of management of innovative processes in the field of information and communication technologies.

Table 2**Current situation analysis on the methodology for assessing the effectiveness of management of innovative processes in the field of ICT⁸**

№	Indicators	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022
1	Innovative communication indicators	6	6.5	8	10.5	11
2	Indicators of human capital involved in innovation processes	5.5	5.5	5.5	5.5	7.5
3	Digital business indicators	5	5	5	6	6
4	Indicators of innovative goods and services	5.5	5.5	5.5	6	7
5	Integral indicator	22	22.5	24	28	31.5

⁷ Based on data from the Ministry of Information Technologies and Communications of the Republic of Uzbekistan

⁸ Analyzed by the authors

The table below provides an analysis of the current situation in the field of ICT in the field of innovation process management effectiveness assessment methodology. According to the methodology proposed by the author, the integral indicator for the current situation is 31.5.

In foreign countries, ICT indicators are reflected in many international rankings of the country and determine the level of development of the country. At the same time, the share of the ICT sector in the country's GDP reflects the level of development of the country. A comparative analysis of these indicators is given in the table below. (Table 3)

Table 3

Analysis of ICT rankings in foreign countries and the share of ICT in GDP

States	2018		2019		2020		2021		2022	
	U _{yaim}	X _{ro}								
Korea	11.8	3	12	3	12.3	4.3	12.5	4.6	12.7	5.3
United States	6.8	8	7.4	6.3	7.7	6.3	8.2	6	8.6	6.3
United Kingdom	6.9	10.3	7.1	10.6	8.6	11.6	10.7	11.3	12.4	11
Sweden	7	6.6	8.6	7	8.8	4.3	9.1	4	9.2	5.5
Finland	7.9	12.6	8.3	12.3	8.7	11	8.9	11	9.1	15.3
Denmark	4.8	47.6	5.3	46.6	5.6	44.6	6.1	45.6	6.6	43.6
Germany	4.1	40.3	6.3	41	8.15	41	8.45	41	8.6	42.6
Russia	2.1	103.5	2.5	103	2.8	98	2.8	96.6	3	95.3
Kazakhstan	2	53	2.1	53.3	2.8	55	3.1	56.6	3.9	52.6
Uzbekistan	1,2	91.5	1.5	87.5	1.7	88	2.2	88	2.3	91.6

Note: here

U_{yaim} - share in GDP

X_{ro} - Average place in international rankings

The analysis of the rating indicators of the ICT sector in foreign countries and the share of the ICT sector in GDP shows that the international The share of the ICT sector in the country's GDP is also high in the countries ranked high in the rankings.

The author analyzes the share of ICT in GDP in the country and international rankings. (Table 4).

Table 4

Analysis of integrated indicators of effective management of innovative processes in the field of ICT⁹

Show small	GII	IDI	EGDI	GCI	Integral indicator	GDP billion	ICT GDP share%
2018	2 1, 80	4.48	0.48	0.27	6 , 75	81,779	1,2
2019	2 2, 49	4.90	0.56	0.27	7, 05	59,16	1.5
2020	2 3, 12	4.90	0.62	0.46	7, 2 7	50,393	1.7
2021	2 3, 84	4.92	0.66	0.56	7, 49	57,921	2.2
2022	24.54	4.95	0.69	0.66	7.71	60,374	2.3

⁹ Developed by the authors

The authors conducted a series of analyzes to study the management of innovation processes of Uzbektelecom JSC as an object of research and the impact of investments in innovation on the net profit of the company. Net profit (u) depends on a number of factors that affect it, including innovation processes. Using correlation-regression analysis, we analyze the factors influencing innovation processes and, ultimately, the positive or negative impact of innovation processes on net profit.

Table 5

Forecast indicators on the methodology for assessing the effectiveness of management of innovative processes in the field of ICT¹⁰

№	Name of indicators	2022	2023	2024	2025	2030
1	Innovative communication indicators	14.7	15.5	18.5	20	22
2	Indicators of human capital involved in innovation processes	7.5	8	9	15	23
3	Digital business indicators	11	13	15	15	20
4	Indicators of innovative goods and services	7.5	9	14	16	22
5	Integral indicator	40.7	45.5	56.5	66	87

According to the forecast, the integrated indicator in 2030 will be 87 points, which is an increase of 2.5 times compared to the current situation.

As a result of managing the innovative activities of Uzbektelecom JSC, the authors have developed forecast indicators of net profit until 2030.

Figure 4. Forecast indicators of net profit of Uzbektelecom JSC until 2030¹¹

Figure 4 shows the forecast of net profit of Uzbektelecom JSC until 2030. In 2030, net profit will increase 2.8 times compared to 2020.

Conclusion

It can be seen from the regression model that the net profit of Uzbektelecom JSC depends on the amount of investments in innovations. If innovations are not introduced into the company's operations, net profit will decrease.

¹⁰Developed by the author

¹¹Developed by the author

“ Information and communication technologies in Uzbekistan **The authors** proposed a model for the formation of a group of indicators that are sources of information in the provision of information at each stage of the management of innovation processes in the field of information and communication technologies and used to monitor the management of innovation processes .

In this model, the following indicators are used for monitoring:

1. Indicators of the stage of problem identification and formation of an innovative idea:

- Analysis of online applications and problem identification;
- study of competitors;
- Analysis of the activities of foreign companies;

2. Indicators of the stage of development and preparation of technical documentation:

- Percentage of innovation process management concept planning;
- Percentage of development and organization of the management concept;
- Percentage of documentation to start the implementation of innovation processes;

3. Indicators of the management phase of the implementation of innovation processes:

- Choosing the form of management of innovation processes - the formation of a working group and the appointment of officials;

- Control and regulation of innovation processes;
- Presentation of the results of innovative processes in production;

4. Indicators of presentation of results of innovative processes:

- launch the demo version;
- conducting marketing research in test mode;

5. Technology transfer and commercialization indicators:

- determine the directions of public presentation;
- attract investment in transfer and advertising costs.

Management of innovative processes of Uzbektelecom JSC determines the directions of their future efficiency:

1. Mastering new technologies. Leadership in transport networks, network ownership and information technology infrastructure.

2. Development of innovative products and services. Unified content management system: cloud technologies, distributed infrastructure services and other similar modern services.

3. Innovations in management. Increase competitiveness in the global market and reduce large costs.

4. Energy efficiency and ecology. Leadership and high social responsibility in cost management.

The stages of the roadmap for the management of innovation processes of Uzbektelecom JSC will be implemented in three stages.

Step 1. System formation. Implementation period is 2021-2023. During this period, the company will modernize the material and technical base, make changes in the organizational structure of the company, improve production and services, develop a

system of employee incentives, develop and implement innovative processes and related information. measures will be developed.

Step 2. The stage of achieving results. Implementation period is 2023-2025. This stage includes the effective use of existing opportunities, the training of personnel with the skills and competencies to work with competitive, modern equipment and technology, the integration of science and industry, as well as cooperation with foreign companies.

Step 3. The transition to a new era. Designed for 2025-2030.

A software product of the methodology for assessing the effectiveness of innovation process management in the field of ICT has been developed. This software product allows you to manage and monitor innovation processes. These indicators allow us to monitor the dynamics of changes in the results of innovation process management each year.

References:

1. Abdullaev, A.M. (2021). The problems of assessing the competitiveness of small businesses. *Nazariy va amaliy tadqiqotlar xalqaro jurnali*, 1 (1), 22-31.
2. Abdullayeva, B. Y. (2022). Повышение эффективности инновационных процессов на предприятиях текстильной промышленности. *Nazariy va amaliy tadqiqotlar xalqaro jurnali*, 2(4), 107-115.
3. Achilov, A. N. (2014). Primenenie teorii ciklichnosti jekonomicheskikh processov vneshnej sredy v strategicheskom upravlenii predpriyatiem. *Zhurnal nauchnyh publikacij aspirantov i doktorantov*, (5 (95)), 31.
4. Achilov, A. N. (2016). Accounting for inventory at the enterprises of the republic of Uzbekistan. *ISJ Theoretical & Applied Science*, 4(36), 181.
5. Achilov, A. N. (2016). Problemy buhgalterskogo uchjota tovarno-material'nyh zapasov i puti ih reshenija. *Zhurnal nauchnyh publikacij aspirantov i doktorantov*, (5), 81.
6. Achilov, A. N. (2018). O'zbekiston Respublikasi iqtisodiyotida kimjo sanoatining tutgan o'ri, ahamijati, muammolari va tovar-moddiy zahiralarni hisobga olishni takomillashtirish masalalari. *Iktisod va molija. Ilmij-amaliy zhurnal*, (4), 25.
7. Achilov, A. N. (2019). Accounting for inventory at the chemical industry of the republic of Uzbekistan. *Theoretical & Applied Science*, (11), 5-7.
8. Achilov, A. N., & Payazov, M. M. (2020). Вопросы улучшения социального положения населения республики Узбекистан и качественной организацией коммунальных услуг. *Theoretical & Applied Science*, (5), 708-713.
9. Achilov, A. N., Payazov, M. M., Akbarov, Z. N., & Madaminov, O. B. (2020). Issues to improving the social situation of the population of the republic of Uzbekistan and the qualitative organization of municipal services. *Theoretical & Applied Science*, (05 (85)), 708.
10. Akhunova, M. (2022). Innovatsion rivojlanish strategiyasini joriy etish asosida to'qimachilik sanoatini rivojlantirishning dolzarb masalalari. *Nazariy va amaliy tadqiqotlar xalqaro jurnali*, 2 (9), 20-26.
11. Ashurov, M. S. (2022). Zamonaviy sharoitda O'zbekistonda innovatsion faoliyatning holati va va uni rivojlantirishning ustuvor yo'nalishlari. *Nazariy va amaliy tadqiqotlar xalqaro jurnali*, 2(1), 15-30.

12. Икратов, М.А. (2022). Иқтисодий рақамлаштиришда интеллектуал кадрларни тайёрлаш муаммолари ва ечимлари. *Nazariy va amaliy tadqiqotlar xalqaro jurnali*, 2 (4), 116-121. doi: 10.5281/zenodo.6656746
13. Пуосов, А. А. (2022). Саноат маҳсулотлари экспортининг ташкилий-иқтисодий механизмларини такомиллаштириш (Фарғона вилояти саноат тармоғи мисолида). *Монография. Фарғона, Al-Ferganus*. Doi: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6618980>
14. Ivanovich, K. K. (2020). About some questions of classification of institutional conditions determining the structure of doing business in Uzbekistan. *South Asian Journal of Marketing & Management Research*, 10(5), 17-28.
15. Kurpayanidi, K. (2022). Institutional conditions for the development of entrepreneurship in the context of the transformation of the national economy. *Economic Innovations*, 24(3(84)), 67-76. [https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.31520/ei.2022.24.3\(84\).67-76](https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.31520/ei.2022.24.3(84).67-76)
16. Ачиллов, А. Н. (2018). Мамлакатимизда кимё саноатида товар-моддий захираларнинг сарфини ҳисобга олиш ва уни такомиллаштириш масалалари. *Экономика и финансы (Узбекистан)*, (8).
17. Ачиллов, А. Н. (2019). Кимё саноати корхоналарида товар-моддий захиралар туркумланишининг ўзига хос хусусиятлари ва улар ҳисобини такомиллаштириш масалалари. *Экономика и финансы (Узбекистан)*, (9).
18. Ачиллов, А. Н. (2021). Вопросы совершенствования структуры производства в Узбекистане. *Наука сегодня: проблемы и перспективы развития* (pp. 38-39).
19. Гулямов, С.С., Шермухамедов, А.Т., & Мухитдинова, М. Х (2022). Развитие искусственного интеллекта в Узбекистане. *Nazariy va amaliy tadqiqotlar xalqaro jurnali*, 2 (5), 7-17. doi: 10.5281/zenodo.6945578
20. Ёрматов, И. Т. (2017). Актуальные проблемы повышения инновационного потенциала Узбекистана. *Актуальные проблемы гуманитарных и социально-экономических наук*, 11(5), 70-73.

E'lon / Reklama / Advertisement

ЭЪЛОН

Хурматли ҳамкасабалар “Al-Ferganus” нашриёти ва “Xalqaro nazariy va amaliy tadqiqotlar jurnali” электрон журнали Ўзбекистон таълим хизматлари бозорида ўзининг фаолиятини бошлаганлигини маълум қиламиз.

Ажойиб имкониятдан сиз биринчилар қаторида фойдаланиб илмий нашрларингизни чоп этишингиз мумкин.

“Al-Ferganus” нашриётимиз томонидан Сиз тақдим этган дарслик, ўқув қўлланма, монография ва илмий рисодаларга ISBN, Doi халқаро рақамли идентификаторларни бириктириш, уларнинг электрон замонавий андозадаги муқовалар ва ишланмаларнинг электрон макетини яратиш, нашриётда эълон қилинган ишларни электрон ахборот нашрларида жойлаштириш хизматлари кўрсатилади.

Бизнинг нашриётимизнинг бошқа нашриётлардан фарқи шундаки, тезкор ва сифатли хизмат кўрсатамиз ҳамда энг асосийси биз Сизнинг ишларингизни Алишер Навоий номидаги Ўзбекистон Миллий кутубхонаси ва Россия Миллий кутубхонаси фондларига бепул жойлашга шунингдек, Россия илмий иқтибослик индекси (РИНЦ ва E – library) платформасига, CrossRef базаларига шартнома асосида жойлаштиришга кўмаклашамиз.

“Xalqaro nazariy va amaliy tadqiqotlar jurnali” ISSN 2181-2357 электрон журнали ҳам ўз фаолиятини бошламоқда. Бизнинг журналда Ўзбекистон Республикаси Олий аттестация комиссиясининг куйидаги ихтисосликлари физика-математика, кимё, биология, геология-минералогия, техника, қишлоқ хўжалиги,

тарих, иқтисодиёт, фалсафа, филология, география, юридик, педагогика, тиббиёт санъатшунослик, архитектура, психология, социология фанлари бўйича миллий ва хорижий муаллифларнинг фанлардан эришган ютуқлари ва истиқболлари борасидаги илмий мақолалари, илмий тадқиқотлар олиб бораётган олимларнинг илмий изланишлари натижалари эълон қилинади. Электрон журнал ҳар ойда бир марта эълон қилинади.

Журналларда эълон қилинадиган ҳар бир мақолага шартнома асосида DOI (Crossref) рақами берилади.

Шунингдек, таҳририят томонидан:

- мақолаларни сифатли таржима қилиш;
- мақолаларни таҳрирлаш ва журналлар талабига мослаш;
- мақолаларга ишлов бериш;
- мақолаларни плагиатга текшириш;
- хориждаги нуфузли (Scopus, Web of sciences ва юқори импакт факторли) журналларда мақолларни сифатли ва ишончли чоп этишга кўмаклашиш хизматларини ҳам кўрсатади.

Имкониятни бой бериб қўйманг!

Қуйидаги манзилларга мурожаат қилинг:

Электрон почта манзили: Alferganus.ltd@gmail.com

Телеграмм манзилимиз : @Alferganus_ltd

Телефонлар: (97) 100-38-88

(91) 109-05-38

(97) 337-86-00

PUBLIC IDENTIFIERS OF INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF THEORETICAL AND PRACTICAL RESEARCH

PUBLISHER: AL-FERGANUS LLC - UZBEKISTAN

INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL ADDRESS^{IJA}

IJA.ZONE/16456457645

INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF THEORETICAL AND PRACTICAL RESEARCH^{IJA}

INTERNATIONAL ARTICLE ADDRESS^{IAA}

IJA.ZONE/1264564543

INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF THEORETICAL AND PRACTICAL RESEARCH^{IAA}

License type supported CC: Attribution 4.0 International (CC BY 4.0)

ВНИМАНИЕ ОБЪЯВЛЕНИЕ!

Уважаемые коллеги! Сообщаем вам, что издательский дом «AL-FARGANUS» и «Xalqaro nazariy va amaliy tadqiqotlar jurnali»- «Международный журнал теоретических и прикладных исследований» начали свою деятельность на рынке образовательных услуг Узбекистана.

Это прекрасная возможность одним из первых опубликовать свои научные публикации. Наше издательство «AL-FARGANUS» предоставляет услуги по прикреплению международных цифровых идентификаторов ISBN, Doi к учебникам, учебным пособиям, монографиям и научным брошюрам, созданию электронных макетов их обложек и дизайнов в современной электронной форме, размещению опубликованных работ в электронные публикации.

Отличие нашего издательства от других издательств в том, что мы предоставляем быстрые и качественные услуги, а главное, бесплатно размещаем ваши работы в Национальной библиотеке Узбекистана им. Алишера Навои и оказываем помощь в размещении вашей работы в Российской национальной библиотеке, а также на платформе Российского индекса научного цитирования (РИНЦ, e-library) облегчить размещение.

Совместно с Ферганским политехническим институтом запущен проект электронного научного журнала «Xalqaro nazariy va amaliy tadqiqotlar jurnali – International Journal of Theoretical and Practical Research. Международный журнал теоретических и прикладных исследований».

Миссия научного электронного журнала направлена на развитие национальной и зарубежной науки, обеспечение общедоступности теоретических

позиций и практических результатов прикладных исследований. В журнале представлены следующие специальности Высшей аттестационной комиссии Республики Узбекистан по физике и математике, химии, биологии, геологии и минералогии, технике, сельскому хозяйству, истории, экономике, философии, филологии, географии, праву, педагогике, медицине, архитектуре, психологии, социологии. Журнал публикует научные статьи отечественных и зарубежных авторов о достижениях и перспективах науки, результатах научных исследований ученых, проводящих исследования. Электронный журнал издается один раз в месяц.

Каждой статье, опубликованной в журнале, на контрактной основе присваивается номер DOI (Crossref).

Также издательство оказывает услуги по:

- качественный перевод статей;
- редактирование статей и адаптация к требованиям журнала;
- обработка статей;
- проверка научных работ (статей, учебных пособий, монографий, диссертаций и др.) на плагиат статей;
- оказывает информационное обеспечение публикаций статей в престижных зарубежных журналах (Scopus, Web of Sciences и журналах с высоким импакт-фактором).

Не упускайте возможность!

Пожалуйста, свяжитесь с нами:

Электронный адрес: Alferganus.ltd@gmail.com

Наш адрес в телеграмм: @Alferganus_ltd

Телефоны: (97) 100-38-88

(91) 109-05-38

(97) 337-86-00

PUBLIC IDENTIFIERS OF INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF THEORETICAL AND PRACTICAL RESEARCH

PUBLISHER: AL-FERGANUS LLC - UZBEKISTAN

INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL ADDRESS^{IJA}

I J A . Z O N E / 1 6 4 5 6 4 5 7 6 4 5

INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF THEORETICAL AND PRACTICAL RESEARCH^{IJA}

INTERNATIONAL ARTICLE ADDRESS^{IAA}

I J A . Z O N E / 1 2 6 4 5 6 4 5 4 3

INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF THEORETICAL AND PRACTICAL RESEARCH^{IAA}

License type supported CC: Attribution 4.0 International (CC BY 4.0)

2021-06-22 00:02:38

O'zbekiston Respublikasi
Prezidenti
Administratsiyasi
huzuridagi Axborot
va ommaviy
kommunikatsiyalar
agentligi

№ 7430-3360-d0e2-4e5b-8cf1-9914-2923
Hujjat yaratilgan sana: 2021-06-22
Ariza raqami: 32087634

Hujjat berilgan: ОБЩЕСТВО С ОГРАНИЧЕННОЙ
ОТВЕТСТВЕННОСТЬЮ "AL-FERGANUS"
Qabul qiluvchining identifikatsiya raqami: 308291417

Ommaviy axborot vositasi davlat ro'yxatidan o'tkazilganligi to'g'risida
GUVOHNOMA

№ 1189

Nomi: "Xalqaro nazariy va amaliy tadqiqotlar"

Tarqatish shakli: jurnal

Til(lar)i: o'zbek, rus, ingliz

Muassis(lar)i: "AL-FERGANUS" mas'uliyati cheklangan jamiyat

Ixtisoslashuvi: fan sohalaridagi ilmiy nashr

Tahririyat manzili: 150100, Farg'ona viloyati, Farg'ona shahar, Mustaqillik ko'chasi, 42-uy

Tarqatish hududi: O'zbekiston Respublikasi hamda belgilangan tartibda chet davlatlarga

Berilgan sanasi: 17-06-2021

Ro'yxatdan o'tkazuvchi organ rahbari: Xodjayev Asadjon Azatbekovich

Mazkur hujjat Vazirlar Mahkamasining 2017 yil 15 sentyabrdagi 728-son qarori bilan tasdiqlangan O'zbekiston Respublikasi Yagona interaktiv davlat xizmatlari portali to'g'risidagi nizomga muvofiq shakllantirilgan elektron hujjatning nusxasi hisoblanadi. Elektron hujjatning nusxasida ko'rsatilgan ma'lumotlar to'g'riligini tekshirish uchun repo.gov.uz veb-saytiga o'ting va elektron hujjatning noyob raqamini kiriting yoki mobil telefon yordamida QR-kodni skaner qiling. Diqqat! Vazirlar Mahkamasining 2017 yil 15 sentyabrdagi 728-son qaroriga muvofiq elektron hujjatlardagi ma'lumotlar qonuniy hisoblanadi. Davlat organlariga Yagona portalda shakllantirilgan elektron hujjatlarning nusxalarini qabul qilishni rad etishlari qat'iy taqiqlangan.

9103

Our publications

Bizning nashlarimiz

Наши издания

Д.Р.ТҲХАСИНОВА

КОРХОНАЛАРДА ХОДИМЛАРНИ
БОШҚАРИШДА ИННОВАЦИОН УСУЛЛАРДАН
ФОЙДАЛАНИШНИ ТАКОМИЛЛАШТИРИШ

Монография

Farg'ona - AL - FERGANUS - 2022

Тўхтасинова Д.Р
Корхоналарда
ходимларни бошқаришда
инновацион усуллардан
фойдаланишни
такомиллаштириш:
монография / Тўхтасинова
Д.Р. - Фарғона
политехника институти.
Фарғона, AL-FERGANUS,
2022. – 162 б.
ISBN 978-9943-8579-5-7

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7352200>

Kurpayanidi K.I.,

Issues of innovation and
innovation management in
the context of economic
transformation: monograph
/ Kurpayanidi K.I.,
edited by M.A.Ikramov. –
Fergana polytechnic
institute. AL-FERGANUS,
2022. – 280 p.
ISBN 978-9943-8579-2-6

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7220693>

Курпаяниди К. И., Илёсов А.А. Саноат маҳсулотлари экспортнинг ташкилий-иқтисодий механизmlарини такомиллаштириш (Фарғона вилояти саноат тармоғи мисолида): монография / Курпаяниди К. И., Илёсов А.А.; М. А. Икрамов тахрир остида. - Фарғона политехника институти. AL-FERGANUS, 2022. – 184 б. ISBN 978-9943-7707-5-1

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6618980>

Мамуров Э.Т., Гафуров А.М. CAD/CAM/CAE тизимларида лойихалаш асослари. Дарслик /Э.Т.Мамуров, А.М.Гафуров – Фарғона: AL-FERGANUS, 2022.- 200 б.

ISBN 978-9943-7706-9-0

Ўзбекистон Республикаси Олий ва ўрта махсус таълим вазирлиги ҳузуридаги Олий, ўрта махсус ва профессионал таълим йўналишлари бўйича ўқув-услубий бирлашмалар фаолиятини мувофиқлаштирувчи кенгаш томонидан дарслик сифатида тавсия этилган. (2022 йил 9 сентябр №302-сонли буйруқ).

CAD/CAM/CAE TIZIMLARIDA
LOYIXALASH ASOSLARI

Дарслик

Фарғона - AL - FERGANUS - 2022

E.T.Mamurov, Yu.Yu.Xusanov,
S.M.Yusupov

Mexatronika asoslari

Darslik

Farg'ona - AL - FERGANUS - 2022

Mamurov E.T., Xusanov Yu.Yu., Yusupov S.M. Mexatronika asoslari. Darslik/ - E.T.Mamurov, Yu.Yu.Xusanov, S.M.Yusupov - Farg'ona: AL-FERGANUS, 2022. 280 b.
ISBN 978-9943-7707-1-3

O'zbekiston Respublikasi Oliy va o'rta maxsus ta'lim vazirligi huzuridagi Oliy, o'rta maxsus va professional ta'lim yo'nalishlari bo'yicha o'quv-uslubiy birlashmalar faoliyatini Muvofiqlashtiruvchi kengash tomonidan darslik sifatida tavsiya etilgan. (2022 yil 9 sentyabr №302-sonli buyruq).

E.T.Mamurov, S.M.Yusupov,
Yu.Yu.Xusanov

YO'NALISHGA KIRISH

Darslik

Farg'ona - AL - FERGANUS - 2022

Mamurov E.T., Yusupov S.M., Xusanov Yu.Yu. Yo'nalishga kirish. Darslik / E.T.Mamurov, S.M.Yusupov, Yu.Yu.Xusanov - Farg'ona: AL-FERGANUS, 2022.- 150 b.
ISBN 978-9943-7707-0-6

O'zbekiston Respublikasi Oliy va o'rta maxsus ta'lim vazirligi huzuridagi Oliy, o'rta maxsus va professional ta'lim yo'nalishlari bo'yicha o'quv-uslubiy birlashmalar faoliyatini Muvofiqlashtiruvchi kengash tomonidan darslik sifatida tavsiya etilgan. (2022 yil 9 sentyabr №302-sonli buyruq).

**MANAGEMENT OF
INNOVATIVE ACTIVITIES
OF BUSINESS ENTITIES IN
INDUSTRY**

MONOGRAPH

Fergana - AL - FERGANUS - 2022

**Kurpayanidi K.I.,
Mamurov D.E.**
Management of innovative
activity of business entities
in industry: monograph /
Kurpayanidi K.I., Mamurov
D.E.; edited by
M.A.Ikramov. - Fergana
polytechnic institute. AL-
FERGANUS, 2022. – 200 p.
ISBN: 978-9943-7707-3-7

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6475830>

Муминова Э.А.,
Хонкелдиева К.Р.

Тўқимачилик саноати кластерлари
фаолиятида бошқарув механизмларини
такомиллаштириш

Монография

Фарғона - AL - FERGANUS - 2022

**Муминова Э.А.,
Хонкелдиева К.Р.**
Тўқимачилик саноати
кластерлари
фаолиятида бошқарув
механизмларини
такомиллаштириш
[Матн]: монография
/Э.А.Муминова,
К.Р.Хонкелдиева.-
Фарғона политехника
институти. Фарғона: AL-
FERGANUS, 2022.-166 б.
ISBN: 978-9943-7707-7-5

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6759902>

РАХМОНАЗАРОВ П.Й.

Худудларнинг иқтисодий - экологик
тизимларини бошқариш самарадорлигини
ошириш

Монография

Фарғона - AL - FERGANUS - 2022

Рахмоназаров П.Й.
Худудларнинг иқтисодий - экологик тизимларини бошқариш самарадорлигини ошириш: монография / Рахмоназаров П.Й. - Фарғона политехника институти. AL-FERGANUS, 2022. – 170 б. ISBN 978-9943-7707-6-8

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6750455>

Ashurov, M. S. Sanoat korxonalarida risklarni boshqarish mexanizmini takomillashtirish strategiyalari. Monografiya. Farg'ona: Al-Ferganus, 2022.- 120 b.

Ashurov Maxammadjon Sotvoldievich

Sanoat korxonalarida risklarni boshqarish
mexanizmini takomillashtirish strategiyalari

Monografiya

Farg'ona - AL - FERGANUS - 2022

A.M. Abdullaev, K.I. Kurpayanidi,
A.Sh. Khudaykulov

INSTITUTIONAL TRANSFORMATION OF THE
ENTREPRENEURIAL SECTOR

Monograph

Fergana - AL - FERGANUS - 2021

**Abdullaev A.M.,
Kurpayanidi K. I.,
Khudaykulov A. S.**
Institutional transformation
of the business sector.
Monograph. Fergana "AL-
FERGANUS", 2021. - 180
p.
ISBN: 978-9943-7189-9-
9

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5457089>

M.S. Ashurov,
K.I. Kurpayanidi

RAQOBATBARDOSH MILLIY INNOVATSIYA
TIZIMINI SHAKLLANTIRISH
MUAMMOLARI VA YECHIMLARI

Monografiya

Farg'ona - AL - FERGANUS - 2021

**Ashurov, M.S.,
Kurpayanidi, K.I.**
Problems and solutions for
the formation of a
competitive national
innovation system.
Monograph. Edited by
Doctor of Economics,
Professor Ikramov M.A.,
Fergana: Al-Ferganus,
2021.- 102 p.
ISBN: 978-9943-7706-0-7

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5676027>

ASHUROV M.S., SHAKIROVA Yu. S.

EKOLOGIK MUAMMOLAR VA ULARNI HAL
QILISHDA EKOLOGIK MENEJMENTNING
STRATEGIK YO'NALISHLARI

Monografiya

Farg'ona - AL - FERGANUS - 2021

Ashurov M.S., Shakirova Yu.S. Environmental problems and strategic directions of environmental management in their solution. Monograph. Edited by Doctor of Economics, Professor Ikramov M.A., Fergana: Al-Ferganus, 2021.- 160 p.
ISBN: 978-9943-7706-4-5

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5722678>

Н.Қ. Жўраева

Уй-жой коммунал соҳаси фаолиятини
бошқариш механизмларини такомиллаштириш
Монография

Фарғона - AL - FERGANUS - 2021

Жўраева, Н.Қ. Уй-жой коммунал соҳаси фаолиятини бошқариш механизмларини такомиллаштириш. Монография. - Фарғона: Al-Ferganus, 2021.- 140 б.
ISBN: 978-9943-7189-8-2

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5335878>

А.Т. Мирзаев
ЎЗБЕКИСТОНДА ТУРИСТИК-РЕКРЕАЦИЯ
ФАОЛИЯТИНИ БОШҚАРИШНИНГ УСЛУБИЙ
ЖИХАТЛАРИ: ЎЗГАРИШЛАР ВА
ИСТИҚБОЛЛАР

Монография

Фарғона - AL - FERGANUS - 2021

Mirzaev, A.T.
Methodological aspects of
tourism and recreational
activity management in
Uzbekistan: changes and
prospects: Monograph
/Mirzaev A.T.; ed G. Sh.
Khankeldiyeva - Fergana:
Al-Ferganus, 2021.- 174 p.
ISBN: 978-9943-7706-3-8

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5722700>

Э.А.Муминова

ТЎҚИМАЧИЛИК САНОАТИ КОРХОНАЛАРИДА
КОРПОРАТИВ БОШҚАРУВНИ ИННОВАЦИОН
ПАРАДИГМАСИ: МЕТОДОЛОГИЯ, ТАЖРИБА
ВА РИВОЖЛАНИШ ИСТИҚБОЛЛАРИ

Монография

Фарғона - AL - FERGANUS - 2021

Muminova, E.A.
Innovative paradigm of
corporate governance at
textile enterprises:
methodology, experience
and development prospects:
monograph /Muminova
E.A.; ed. G. Sh.
Khankeldiyeva - Fergana:
Al-Ferganus, 2021.- 160 p.
ISBN: 978-9943-7706-1-4

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5676091>

Набиева, Н.М. Хизмат кўрсатиш корхоналарини ривожлантиришнинг маркетинг стратегиясини ишлаб чиқиш. Монография. - Фарғона: Al-Ferganus, 2021.- 162 б. ISBN: 978-9943-7189-7-5

Н.М. Набиева
Хизмат кўрсатиш корхоналарини ривожлантиришнинг маркетинг стратегиясини ишлаб чиқиш

Монография

Фарғона - AL - FERGANUS - 2021

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5230368>

Nazarmatov, O.S. Improving the methodology of management of innovative processes in the enterprises of the textile industry. Monograph. - Fergana: Al-Ferganus, 2021.- 200 p. ISBN: 978-9943-7706-2-1

О.С.Назарматов

ТЎҚИМАЧИЛИК САНОАТИ КОРХОНАЛАРИДА
ИННОВАЦИОН ЖАРАЁНЛАРНИ БОШҚАРИШ
УСЛУБИЁТИНИ ТАКОМИЛЛАШТИРИШ

Монография

Фарғона - AL - FERGANUS - 2021

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5675967>

UBAYDULLAYEV M.M.

G'O'ZADA DEFOLIATSIYA O'TKAZISHNING
MAQBUL ME'YOR VA MUDDATLARI

Monografiya

Farg'ona - AL - FERGANUS - 2021

Ubaydullayev M.M.
G'o'zada defoliatsiya
o'tkazishning maqbul
me'yor va muddatlari.
Monografiya. /q.x.f.d.,
professor F.J. Teshayev
muharrirligi ostida.
Farg'ona: Al-Ferganus,
2021. – 160 b.

ISBN: 978-9943-7706-6-9

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5722721>

